

SYRIUS

HYDROGEN FOR SUSTAINABLE STEEL

Integrating a Solid Oxide Electrolyser for green hydrogen production supplying a reheating furnace to reduce CO₂ emissions from steelmaking process

Co-funded by
the European Union

Partners

kiwa

Baker Hughes

tenova

RWTH AACHEN
UNIVERSITY

Arvedi AST

Objective

SYRIUS aims at **integrating a SOE** in a reheating furnace in a real steel manufacturing plant, **dropping down electric consumptions and CO₂ emissions** while enabling heat recovery and circularity.

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